

AN APPROACH OF CORROSION RESISTANT SMART MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: In recent years, researches on intellectual structure systems called "Smart materials", having the function of self-diagnosis or self-restoration similar to that of biomimetic systems, have been made in the field of aerospace or civil engineering. Smart materials are constituted by a sensor part, a processor part, and an actuator part. There are many researches about sensors, but only a few researches mentioned about actuators. On the other hand, there is a corrosion behavior type of polymeric materials so-called "penetration type". In this type, environment penetrates into materials much faster than reaction take place. Thus, in this type, there is a possibility to prevent from degradation by penetrated environment removal from materials before reaction occurs. In this study, the authors tried to remove volatile and nonvolatile environment from polymeric materials by using water.

KEY WORDS: intellectual structure, smart materials, self-diagnosis, self-restoration, biomimetic, actuator, hollow fiber.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, composite materials become widely used as engineering structures. Many researchers are dealing with health monitoring of mechanical damage in composite structures. Although there are various unique methods of health monitoring, optical fiber sensor is still attracting major attention (e.g. Haga et al. [1]). Optical fiber sensor embedded in matrix resin can monitor internal strain, microcracks or interlaminar fracture of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) laminates. Buerck et al. [2] made a trial of detection of hydrocarbon leakage by using polymer-clad-silica-core optical fiber connected to optical time domain reflectometer (OTDR).

There are, however, few applications of optical fiber sensor to monitor chemical change. Doyle et al. [3] reported that optical fiber sensor embedded in epoxy resin could monitor a curing process by the measurement of spectrum. Mendoza et al. [4] studied optical fiber sensor with special cladding materials. Moisture absorption to the cladding and change of pH could be detected by the optical fiber sensor. Li et al. [5] manufactured a fiber-optic corrosion sensor, in which the core was exposed and electroplated with Fe-C alloy before immersion in corrosive environment. Refractive index of the sensor changes when Fe-C alloy corroded, and the intensity of output signal increased. The sensor demonstrated a good performance for sensing corrosion phenomena. Makedonski et al. [6] synthesized reactive azo dyes as reversible pH sensors and made thin films with polyvinyl alcohol matrix. These thin films are available as pH sensor in concrete structure. Even though these research works are significant, it is difficult to detect the penetration of both acidic and alkaline solution and difficult to evaluate the corrosion quantitatively.

Some articles mentioned about using hollow fibers as actuators. Bleay et al. [7] proposed self-repairing system by means of embedding hollow fibers containing uncured resin.

The corrosion behavior of thermosetting resin [8], the health monitoring of chemical degradation [9, 10], and the removal of penetrated methanol from unsaturated polyester resin using ventilation through hollow fiber [11] have been investigated in our laboratory.

Because ventilation can remove only volatile environment, experiment is performed using water instead of ventilation to remove not only volatile but also nonvolatile environment in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two types of resin were used: orthophthalic acid type unsaturated polyester resin (UP) and the second is amine curing type epoxy resin (EP). UP was cured with 1phr methyl ethyl ketone peroxide and 0.5phr naphthex cobalt. EP was cured with 50phr amine curing agent and 0.1phr antifoaming agent.

Both resins were cast into 2mm thick plate and then cured at 50°C for 2hours for UP and at 20°C for 24hours for EP. Then the cured plates were cut into specimen with 25mm width and 60mm length. After cutting, specimens were postcured 2hours at 100°C and 80°C, respectively, and tested.

Testing methods

Two steps simple immersion tests were performed. First, UP samples were immersed into two environments that is pure methanol and ethanol, however, EP samples were immersed into 0.5M H₂SO₄ solution (pH=1.0). Testing temperature was kept at 50°C. Specimens at regular time interval were picked up, wiped and then weighted. Secondly, specimens were immersed again into deionized water at 50°C and weight change was measured regularly. For EP specimens, flexural strength and flexural modulus were measured by three point bending test using Simadzu Autograph.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UP resin

To compare with the result of experiment using ventilation, UP specimens were immersed in deionized water after immersion into methanol to remove penetrated methanol. Fig. 1 shows the weight change of specimen immersed in (a) methanol and (b) ethanol, and then in water. Weight change caused by immersion into alcohol is displayed by dotted line, and by immersion into water is displayed by solid line. It is noticed that the weight of the specimens immersed into methanol increased sharply until 50hours, and then drop gradually with time.

On the other hand, the weight of the specimen immersed in ethanol shows a gradually increase as time progresses. However, in both cases, the weight change seems to level off at approx. 6-7% gain after the specimens were immersed in water.

Furthermore, penny-shaped crack was observed inside of specimen immersed in water using optical microscope as shown in Fig. 2, it is to be noted that, specimens immersed just in alcohol doesn't present any crack.

Penetrated water stored in this crack, and environmental water dissolves alcohol from inside of the specimen, this may explain the weight convergence subscribed above.

Alcohol removal using water creates this cracks, which may damage more the polymeric materials, therefore, it is unsuitable to remove the penetrated alcohol by water and more suitable methods have to be investigated.

Fig. 1 Weight change of specimen immersed in, (a) methanol (b) ethanol, before water.

Fig. 2 Photograph of penny-shaped crack appeared at inside of specimen after immersion in methanol 96h before water immersion.

EP resin

EP resin specimens were immersed in sulfuric acid and then in water. The weight change is shown in Fig. 3. As for UP, weight change caused by immersion into sulfuric acid is displayed by dotted line, and by immersion into water is displayed by solid line.

It is noticed a decrease in pH of the water used in the immersion of the specimens immersed previously in sulfuric acid, therefore it can be said that the penetrated sulfuric acid has removed by immersion in water. Thus, it was supposed that the weight change will level off to the one with epoxy saturated water only. However, it was observed that the weight change decrease to certain level and then level off without reaching this minimum level. Thus, it can

be said that there are at least two types of sulfuric acid which penetrated into EP resin: one is free from EP resin that it is easy to remove by using water, and the other has some combination with EP resin that it is difficult to remove by using water. We called this operation “wash” for ease.

Fig. 3 Weight change of specimen immersed in sulfuric acid and water.

To investigate the effect of ion combination of the sulfuric acid with EP resin on the mechanical properties, a three-point bending test was performed for specimens before immersion, saturated with water, saturated with sulfuric acid, and washed. Each result is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Mechanical properties of each specimen; (a) flexural strength (b) flexural modulus.

In this graph, both strength and modulus drop considerably after saturation with sulfuric acid. However, both of them recover significantly after washing. Therefore, washing has been proved to be very effective to recover materials’ mechanical properties.

CONCLUSION

UP resin immersed into methanol/ethanol and then immersed into deionized water shows first a gain in the weight before leveling to 6-7% after immersion in water.

Penny-shaped crack caused by water in UP resin make water not suitable for discharging alcohol.

Immersion of the sulfuric-acid-saturated EP resin into water remove free sulfuric acid but water cannot remove the sulfuric acid which has some combination with EP resin.

Mechanical properties of EP resin decreased by saturating with sulfuric acid, but were recovered to certain level by immersing into water.

There is a possibility of restoration by removing penetrated environment from “penetration type” materials using hollow fiber with water or any other agent.

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